
Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning for LLM-Based Arabic-to-English Machine Translation

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Abstract

Large Language Models (LLMs) such as GPT-3, BLOOM, BERT... have revolutionized natural language processing (NLP), particularly in translation. However, fine-tuning these models for downstream tasks, such as Arabic-to-English translation, requires extensive computational resources. Traditional full fine-tuning methods that involve updating all parameters of the model pose significant computational and memory challenges, notably for models with billions of parameters. This study investigates the application of LoRA-based PEFT methods on two chosen models for Arabic to English translation, AraT5 and NLLB-200, with a focus on understanding the trade-offs between computational efficiency and translation quality.

Keywords: Large Language models, Efficiency, Computational challenges, Parameter-efficient fine-tuning, Arabic-to-English Machine translation.

1 Introduction

The advent of LLMs has revolutionized the field of natural language processing, they have large numbers of parameters and complex architectures to capture intricate language patterns, making them highly effective in translation tasks that need nuanced understanding and generation. Yet, fine-tuning LLMs for specific tasks requires enormous computational resources. Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning (PEFT) techniques have emerged to mitigate these challenges by selectively adjusting a small subset of parameters. Among PEFT methods, Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) and its variants stand out for their effectiveness, by introducing low-rank matrices to specific layers, allowing the model to learn task-specific adaptations efficiently. Quantized methods go further by quantizing the parameters involved in fine-tuning. Our study focuses on LLMs with encoder-decoder architecture: AraT5 and NLLB-200, which are ideal for Arabic-to-English translation. By applying the previous techniques, we aim to capture the trade-offs between computational efficiency and model performance in machine translation.

Our key contributions are:

1. We apply LoRA, DoRA, QLoRA, and QDoRA techniques to fine-tune the AraT5 and NLLB-200 models for Arabic-to-English translation.
2. We assess the computational efficiency of these methods, comparing them to traditional full fine tuning.
3. We evaluate translation quality across the different fine-tuning methods, examining the trade-offs between efficiency and performance.

This paper is organized as follows: The first section reviews LLM-based machine translation approaches, the second section details parameter-efficient fine-tuning techniques, the third section presents our methodology, chosen datasets and models, and the fourth section compares resource usage and translation quality across methods and models.

2 Related works

Machine Translation has undergone significant transformation recently, primarily due to the rapid advancements in LLMs. These advancements have pushed research into LLM-based machine translation, focusing on two main paradigms: In-Context Learning (ICL) and Finetuning.

ICL leverages optimal in-context examples [2] [36] [18], dictionary knowledge [13] [25], adaptive learning

[35] [27], and translation memories [34] to enhance translation accuracy. Traditional machine translation models, particularly those using statistical methods, struggle with contextually rich languages like Arabic, which demand effective capture of long-range dependencies and contextual nuances. Recent advancements in context-aware neural machine translation models, particularly those using self-attention mechanisms, have shown better performance by dynamically focusing on different parts of the input sentence and its context. These models benefit from incorporating larger context windows and external contextual information, such as linguistic annotations and discourse relations, significantly improving the translation quality.

Concurrently, finetuning has been instrumental in augmenting LLM’s capability to translate unseen languages and domains [42] [26] and in building multilingual models [44] [46]. Additionally, research has delved into post-editing translation outcomes [28] [33] and utilizing LLMs for machine translation evaluation [12] [11]. The finetuning process for Arabic to English involves adapting pre-trained LLMs, such as T5, to the specific requirements of the translation task. This process includes further training on parallel Arabic-English datasets, which helps the model capture the syntactic, semantic, and contextual intricacies of both languages. Techniques like domain adaptation, advanced regularization methods, back-translation, and self-training enhance the performance and robustness of the finetuned models. The quality and size of the parallel corpus are crucial for achieving high translation accuracy, highlighting the importance of high-quality, diverse, and representative sentence pairs in the training data.

Recent advancements in multilingual machine translation have shown significant improvements in performance across various language families, including Afro-Asiatic languages and specific language pairs such as Arabic to English. Zhu et al. (2023) [45] evaluated several LLMs on the FLORES-101 dataset [14] using the SentencePiece BLEU (spBLEU) metric (both SentencePiece BLEU and sacreBLEU are libraries used for calculating BLEU scores). For Afro-Asiatic languages (which include Arabic), LLaMA2-7B [39] achieved the highest BLEU score of 57.72, followed by XGLM-7.5B [22] at 54.51 and Falcon-7B [3] at 38.62. Focusing on the Arabic-English pair, GPT-4 performed better than ChatGPT, with scores of approximately 45 and 40 respectively. These results come from remarkably large models, which explains the high BLEU score results.

3 Parameter-efficient Fine-tuning (PEFT)

PEFT adapts an LLM to downstream tasks by freezing the entire LLM backbone and updating only a small set of newly introduced parameters. PEFT methods can be classified into four categories: low-rank adaptation (LoRA [17]), adapter-based tuning (inserting trainable modules into LLMs to simplify fine-tuning [16]), prefix tuning (adding trainable vectors to each LLM layer that are adapted to specific tasks [21]), and prompt tuning (adjusting only the input layer by incorporating trainable prompt tokens that can be placed at the beginning or within the input text [20]).

PEFT methods necessitate careful consideration of several factors to balance performance and efficiency effectively. A major challenge lies in minimizing trainable parameters while maintaining Substantial performance [30]. Fine-tuning too few parameters can restrict the model’s adaptability to the target task, while excessive fine-tuning can degrade the computational advantages of PEFT [9] [24]. The success of PEFT also relies on the quality and quantity of data available, particularly in domains with limited or noisy data where achieving the same accuracy as full fine-tuning can be tough. In such cases, careful selection of data augmentation techniques and transfer learning strategies is important [8] [4].

3.1 Low Rank Adaptation (LoRA)

Low-Rank Adaptation [17], proposed by Hu et al. (2021), is a widely used Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning approach aimed to optimize the adaptation of LLMs to specific tasks. During full fine-tuning, the model is initialized to pre-trained weights W_0 and updated to $W_0 + \Delta W$. The basic hypothesis behind LoRA is that during fine-tuning, A low-rank approximation can powerfully capture the necessary adjustments to the model’s weights. This means that the changes in the weight matrix resulting from task-specific adaptation have a low ”intrinsic rank” [1]. As shown in Figure 3 the information contained within the ΔW matrix can be represented using fewer dimensions than the original matrix and therefore, the full-dimensional update can be approximated by a product of two smaller matrices while keeping the original weights frozen.

Figure 1: Comparison between the traditional fine-tuning approach and the LoRA method

3.1.1 Mathematical Formulation

Considering a pre-trained weight matrix W of a neural network. During fine-tuning, instead of updating W directly, LoRA introduces two trainable low-rank matrices $A \in R^{m \times r}$ and $B \in R^{r \times n}$. The weight update is then formulated as :

$$W_{updated} = W + \Delta W = W + AB \quad (1)$$

Here, r is the rank, a hyperparameter that defines the dimensionality of the low-rank approximation. Using this approach, the amount of trainable parameters is remarkably decreased, as only the matrices A and B need to be learned, while the original weight matrix W remains frozen. This makes the fine-tuning process much more memory and computation efficient.

3.1.2 Reparametrization and Optimization

LoRA modifies the forward pass of the neural network by adding the low-rank update $\Delta W = AB$ to the original output. Specifically, if the original output is $h = W_0x$, the updated output becomes:

$$W_{updated} = W_0x + \Delta Wx = W_0x + ABx \quad (2)$$

In practice, during backpropagation, the frozen pre-trained weights W_0 remain untouched, and the loss is only used to update the B and A matrices introduced by LoRA. A is initialized with a random Gaussian distribution, while B is initialized to zero, ensuring that the initial value of ΔW is zero. The scaling factor α is introduced to balance the contribution of ΔW during training, which is crucial for controlling the impact of the low-rank updates and making sure that the fine-tuning process remains stable and effective.

3.1.3 Applying LoRA to a Transformer

In a transformer architecture of an LLM, it is more common to apply LoRA to the attention layers because they are computationally expensive and have a significant number of parameters, which makes them the prime targets for parameter-efficient fine-tuning. However, it's not limited to just attention layers; it could also be applied to other layers like feed-forward networks.

LoRA allows the fine-tuning process to require fewer parameters and less computational power while still achieving strong performance. However, as with many advancements in AI, researchers have recently introduced other innovative alternatives and derivatives of LoRA, such as DoRA [23], LoRA+ [15], QA-LoRA [41], QLoRA [6], QDoRA [23], and DyLoRA [40], depending on the model architecture itself and the area of focus.

3.2 Weight-Decomposed Low-Rank Adaptation (DoRA)

Weight-Decomposed Low-Rank Adaptation [23] was introduced and built on LoRA by introducing a decomposition of the weight matrix into two components to fine tune them: magnitude and direction, as illustrated in Figure 2. This decomposition separates the fine-tuning of these components, addressing issues in LoRA to make subtle adjustments to weight directions while efficiently handling parameter updates. The process behind DoRA is divided into two main steps. First, the weight matrix W_0 from a pretrained model is decomposed into two components:

Figure 2: An overview of DoRA [23].

- Magnitude Vector m : This vector represents the norm or length of each column in the weight matrix, capturing the scale information.
- Directional Matrix V : Where each column vector of the weight matrix is normalized by dividing by its magnitude, keeping only the directional information.

Once the pretrained weights are decomposed, and given the substantial size of the directional component in terms of parameters, LoRA is applied exclusively to the directional matrix V , and m is trained as it is, which is feasible because it has just one dimension.

DoRA improves both the learning capacity and stability of LoRA, without causing any additional inference overhead. It enables fine-tuning a pretrained model in a way that is computationally efficient and potentially more responsive to new data, maintaining the strengths of the original model while adapting it to new tasks or datasets.

3.3 Quantized Low rank adaptation (QLoRA)

QLoRA reduces the memory footprint of LLMs by compressing weights from high-precision data types such as 32-bit floating point to lower-precision formats such as 4-bit integers or NormalFloat, while integrating trainable Low-Rank Adapters (LoRA) for fine-tuning. The pretrained weights remain frozen, and only the LoRA parameters are updated, minimizing memory requirements. During computational tasks, weights stored as 4-bit NormalFloat are dequantized to 16-bit BrainFloat (bfloat16) for both the forward and backward passes. However, only the LoRA parameter's gradients are computed. QLoRA achieves high-fidelity 4-bit fine tuning via two proposed techniques 4-bit NormalFloat (NF4) Quantization and Double Quantization. Paged Optimizers were also introduced to prevent memory spikes during gradient checkpointing from causing out-of-memory errors that have traditionally made fine tuning on a single machine difficult for large models.

3.3.1 4-bit NormalFloat Quantization

The NormalFloat (NF) data type builds on Quantile Quantization [5] which is an information-theoretically optimal data type that ensures each quantization bin has an equal number of values assigned from the input tensor. Quantile quantization works by estimating the quantile of the input tensor through the empirical cumulative distribution function. This technique helps compress model weights effectively, but the process of quantile estimation is computationally expensive. Fast quantile approximation algorithms, such as SRAM quantiles, help mitigate this cost, but approximation errors arise, especially for outliers, which are often critical.

QLoRA addresses these issues by recognizing that pre-trained LLM weights typically follow a zero-centered normal distribution with a standard deviation α . By transforming all weights to fit within a fixed range (e.g., $[-1, 1]$), accurate quantile estimation becomes feasible, eliminating the need for computationally expensive approximation algorithms. The result is the 4-bit NormalFloat (NF4) data type, which is specifically optimized for normally distributed data. It normalizes neural network weights into this fixed range and quantizes them accordingly, enabling precise weight compression with minimal performance loss.

3.3.2 Double Quantization

A method that reduces the average memory footprint by quantizing the quantization constants [7]. This saves approximately 0.37 bits per parameter, which translates to around 3 GB for a 65B model. It further reduces the memory overhead of quantization constants. By quantizing both the model weights and the quantization constants, QLoRA achieves higher memory efficiency without negatively impacting model performance.

3.3.3 Paged Optimizers

Fine-tuning LLMs can also generate memory spikes, primarily when processing long sequences or large mini-batches. QLoRA harnesses Paged Optimizers to handle these spikes efficiently, leveraging [NVIDIA’s unified memory system](#), which automatically transfers memory between the CPU and GPU. When the GPU runs out of memory, data is paged to the CPU and then moved back to the GPU when needed. This seamless paging mechanism guarantees that memory bottlenecks do not interrupt the training process, allowing QLoRA to handle larger models and batch sizes with fewer resources.

3.4 Quantized Weight-Decomposed Low-Rank Adaptation (QDoRA)

QDoRA combines the memory efficiency of QLoRA with the DoRA fine-tuning. QDoRA leverages quantization to compress weights into low-precision formats, significantly reducing memory footprint. However, it goes further by incorporating weight decomposition, as seen in DoRA, to achieve more granular optimization during fine-tuning. This allows QDoRA to maintain both high performance and low computational requirements, making it suitable for fine tuning and training large models like Llama 3 on consumer-grade GPUs.

4 Methodology

In this work, we explore the performance of small-sized LLMs in Arabic-to-English machine translation, focusing specifically on encoder-decoder-based architectures. Our research is based on two publicly available LLMs on [HuggingFace](#): the Arabic-focused [AraT5v2 Base](#) and the multilingual [NLLB-200 distilled-600M](#) models. To evaluate these models, we conducted experiments using the United Nations Parallel Corpus [47] with AraT5v2 [10] and the OPUS-100 corpus [43] with NLLB-200 [38]. Our objective was to evaluate the trade-offs between computational resource efficiency, such as GPU power consumption and memory allocation, and translation performance using BLEU, and ROUGE and Perplexity scores, without an explicit aim to improve translation quality. We applied four fine-tuning techniques in addition to Full fine-tuning (which served as a baseline used for comparison): LoRA, DoRA, and quantized variants: QLoRA and QDoRA.

4.1 Experiments on AraT5v2 with United Nations Parallel Corpus

We used the United Nations Parallel Corpus with the AraT5v2 model. We adopted the following dataset splitting strategy to ensure a balanced and effective model training, validation, and testing. We started by loading the first 20 000 examples from the corpus. The dataset was split as into:

- Training Set: 15,000 examples (75%) were dedicated to training, ensuring that most of the data is used for model learning.
- Validation Set: 2,500 examples (12.5%) were reserved for validation. This validation set is used to track the model’s performance on unseen data, serving it to prevent overfitting.
- Test Set: 2,500 examples (12.5%) were set aside for testing. The test set is used for the final evaluation.

AraT5v2 built on a foundation set by the original AraT5 model [29]. AraT5 was inspired by the T5 (Text-to-Text Transfer Transformer) model [32], which reframes all NLP tasks into a text-to-text format, offering a unified framework for language modeling tasks.

Tokenization is an important step in converting raw text into a format that a model like AraT5v2 can process. AraT5v2 relies on tokenized inputs for both the source language (Arabic) and the target language (English).

- **Task-Specific Prefix:** The T5 model needs a clear prompt of the task it is performing. In this case, we prepend the Arabic input text with the prefix: "translate Arabic to English: "
- **Tokenization Using AraT5v2's Tokenizer:** We use Hugging Face's [AutoTokenizer](#) to tokenize the Arabic input sentences and their corresponding English translations. AutoTokenizer is a generic tokenizer class in the [Huggingface Transformers library](#) that automatically selects the proper tokenizer for a given model. The original T5 models (including AraT5, which is based on T5) typically use SentencePiece tokenizers [37], which is a text tokenization algorithm widely used in modern NLP models, particularly in models that need to handle complex languages with rich morphology (like Arabic). Unlike traditional tokenizers that split text based on spaces or punctuation, SentencePiece treats the entire text as a continuous stream of characters and learns how to break it into subword units.
- **Truncation and Padding:** To ensure that the input sequences fit within the model's constraints, we limit the maximum sequence length to 128 tokens. Sequences longer than this are truncated, while shorter ones are padded to a uniform length. This ensures consistency across batches during training.

The tokenized dataset consists of pairs of input and output sequences, where each sequence is a list of tokens representing either an Arabic sentence (input) or its English translation (output). These tokenized sequences are then ready for training the AraT5v2 model.

We fine tuned AraT5v2 using different approaches: Full fine-tuning, LoRA, DoRA, and QDoRA:

1. Full fine-tuning means updating all the parameters of the model based on the specific wanted task. We defined several key hyperparameters (used for other techniques as well): Once the training setup

Table 1: Hyperparameters Used for Model Training

Learning rate	$2 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Batch size	2
Number of epochs	5

is complete, the model is trained on the training set by backpropagating through the entire model, including all attention and feed-forward layers, updating every weight in the network. Training is followed by evaluation on the validation set after each epoch to track its performance.

2. We used LoRA to fine-tune AraT5v2, focusing on the following layers involved in the attention mechanism: the key (k), query (q), value (v), and output (o) layers. After freezing the core model parameters, LoRA introduces learnable low-rank matrices that adjust the key, query, value, and output layers of the attention mechanism. These matrices are updated during training, while the original parameters remain untouched. The low-rank structure allows for efficient fine-tuning with fewer parameters to update.
3. In another experiment we applied DoRA by freezing the original model parameters and decomposing the weight matrices involved in the key (k), query (q), value (v), and output (o) layers of the attention mechanism. By applying DoRA to the Target Modules, we decomposed the weight matrices associated with them into their magnitude and directional components. The fine-tuning process updates the directional matrices using LoRA, while the magnitude vector is trained directly. After training, all the components are recombined to form the updated weight matrices which is used for inference.
4. Lastly, QDoRA is applied to the AraT5v2 model by combining two techniques: quantization and Weight Decomposed Low-Rank Adaptation (DoRA). We applied these techniques to the model by quantizing the model's weights to 4-bit precision, then freezing the core weights of the model (from its pre-trained state), the Decomposition of Weights, LoRA is then applied specifically to the directional matrices within the attention layers chosen, and alongside the updates to the directional matrices, the magnitude vector (which represents the scale of the weights) is also fine-tuned. Since the magnitude has significantly fewer parameters, it can be trained directly without requiring the same low-rank approximations used for the directional matrices.

Table 3 summarizes the previous techniques.

4.2 Experiments on NLLB-200 with OPUS-100 Corpus

The NLLB-200 distilled-600M model was fine-tuned using the OPUS-100 dataset. We splitted the dataset into model training, validation, and testing. We started by loading the first 11200 examples from the corpus. The dataset splitting was done as following:

- Training Set: 8000 examples (71%) were dedicated to training.
- Validation Set: 1600 examples (almost 15%) were reserved for validation.
- Test Set: 1600 examples (almost 15%) were set aside for testing.

The NLLB-200-distilled-600M represents a distilled version of the full NLLB-200 model of 600 million parameters. NLLB-200 is an innovative solution to the complex challenges of multilingual machine translation, especially in low-resource languages.

We use a fast tokenizer `NllbTokenizerFast` to process the text, specifying Arabic as the source language (`src_lang`) and English as the target language (`tgt_lang`). It is based on the BytePairEncoding [31], which preserves common words in their full form, while splitting less frequent words into subword units, achieving a balance between vocabulary size and representational efficiency. The tokenizer also handles truncation, ensuring that sentences are cut off at the model’s maximum input length to avoid issues during training. By tokenizing the entire dataset, we prepare it for the subsequent steps.

Once the dataset is prepared, we move on to the fine-tuning stage:

1. Full fine-tuning allows all the layers of the model to be updated during training. The training is configured controlling various aspects (same configuration for other fine tuning methods of the model):

Table 2: Hyperparameters Used for Model Training

Learning rate	$2 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Batch size	1
Number of epochs	3

Evaluation is performed at the end of each epoch.

2. We applied LoRA where instead of updating all the model’s parameters, only the low-rank matrices are updated during fine-tuning, which drastically reduces the number of parameters that need to be trained. In our case, the target layers for LoRA are: Query projection (`q_proj`), Value projection (`V_proj`). Only the low-rank matrices in the `q_proj` and `v_proj` layers are updated, while the rest of the model remains frozen. This reduces the number of trainable parameters while retaining enough capacity to specialize for the translation task.
3. In another experiment, we applied QLoRA which is an advanced version of the original LoRA technique (same as QDoRA). QLoRA focuses on fine-tuning specific layers of the model; this approach extends the benefits of LoRA by further reducing the model’s memory footprint through quantization, while still fine-tuning only a small fraction of the model’s parameters. The core difference in QLoRA is the use of 4-bit quantization that reduces memory requirements even further while maintaining precision for computation.
4. In another experiment, DoRA was applied to fine-tune the NLLB-200 distilled 600M model for Arabic to English translation. By introducing a decomposition of the weight matrix into magnitude and direction, DoRA enhances the fine-tuning process. DoRA allows for independent updates to the scale and directional aspects of the model’s weights. The directional matrix is fine-tuned using LoRA’s low-rank matrices, while the magnitude vector is directly trained.

Table 4 summarizes these techniques.

4.3 Evaluation

To track CPU, GPU and Memory usage, we used Weights & Biases, a platform for machine learning developers to help them build better models faster. It provides lightweight, interoperable tools for

Table 3: AraT5v2 Fine-Tuning Methods

Fine-Tuning Method	Parameters Updated	Low-Rank Dimension (r)	Scaling Factor (lora_alpha)	Dropout (lora_dropout)	Quantization	DoRA Enabled	Full Parameters Updated
Full Fine-Tuning	All Parameters	-	-	-	No	No	Yes
LoRA	Attention Layers (k, q, v, o)	5	32	0.06	No	No	No
DoRA	Magnitude + Direction	5	32	0.06	No	Yes	No
QDoRA	Quantized + Magnitude + Direction	5	32	0.06	Yes	Yes	No

Table 4: NLLB200-600M Fine-Tuning Methods

Fine-Tuning Method	Parameters Updated	Low-Rank Dimension (r)	Scaling Factor (lora_alpha)	Dropout (lora_dropout)	Quantization	DoRA Enabled	Full Parameters Updated
Full Fine-Tuning	All Parameters	-	-	-	No	No	Yes
LoRA	Attention Layers (q, v)	8	32	0.1	No	No	No
DoRA	Magnitude + Direction	8	32	0.1	No	Yes	No
QLoRA	Quantized + Attention Layers (q, v)	8	32	0.1	Yes	No	No

tracking experiments, versioning datasets and models, evaluating model performance, and visualizing results. Additionally to the W&B system tracking, we evaluated the optimization techniques using Perplexity, that measures the model’s uncertainty in generating the next token, the lower the value the better. In addition, we also used the following evaluation metrics: ROUGE-L, which measures the overlap of longest common subsequences between the system output and reference texts, indicating the quality of text summarization or other generation tasks. And SacreBLEU score, which is an extended implementation that builds upon the basic BLEU metric and provides additional features, such as multiple reference support, better handling of tokenization, and more fine-grained control over the evaluation process.

5 Results and discussion

5.1 Models efficiency comparison

Using W&B SDK, we tracked system metrics for every technique on both chosen models.

5.1.1 AraT5v2 Base

In full fine tuning, all the parameters are trained and updated, while Table 5 presents trainable Parameters in the other techniques. Figures 3 and 4 araT5v2 variations showcase varying trade-offs between

Table 5: Comparison of the Trainable Parameters in AraT5v2

Optimization	Trainable Parameters	Total Parameters	Percentage of Trainable Parameters
LoRA	1,105,920	368,614,656	0.30%
DoRA	1,105,920	368,614,656	0.30%
QDoRA	1,216,512	368,725,248	0.33%

power consumption, speed, and resource usage. The full fine tuning of araT5v2 is the fastest, completing

training in 2 hours but consumes high power (around 120W) due to its computational intensity. In contrast, araT5v2-Base-with-LoRA balances speed and resource efficiency, using moderate power (50-60W) while finishing second fastest, making it suitable for scenarios where moderate optimization is needed without heavy resource use. Although araT5v2-Base-with-DoRA was slower than full fine tuning and LoRA, DoRA prioritizes power efficiency over speed by applying more optimized updates (magnitude and direction), making it ideal when power usage is a concern and training time is flexible. Lastly, araT5v2-Base-with-QDoRA is the most power-efficient (60W) but takes over 10 hours to train, which makes it useful for resource-constrained settings where power efficiency is extremely crucial. GPU mem-

Figure 3: GPU power usage in Watt in araT5v2

Figure 4: GPU power usage in % in araT5v2

ory directly impacts real-time performance, determining factors like batch size, computation speed, and

whether the model can fit into memory. During fine-tuning, main components such as model parameters, activations, gradients, and optimizer states are stored in GPU memory. Techniques like LoRA, QLoRA, or QDoRA, which reduce the number of trainable parameters or use quantization, significantly lower GPU memory consumption, allowing larger models to be fine-tuned on more affordable hardware. The graph presented in Figure 5 shows GPU memory allocation, providing insight into how much memory each finetuning method allocates during the training process. The araT5v2 variations exhibit varying

Figure 5: GPU memory allocation in bytes in araT5v2

but stable memory usage based on their tuning strategies. Full fine tuning consumes the most GPU memory (around $8 \cdot 10^9$ bytes) due to its full fine-tuning. LoRA uses less memory (around $3.74 \cdot 10^9$ bytes) by fine-tuning low-rank weight matrices. DoRA is similar to LoRA, using around $4 \cdot 10^9$ bytes, reflecting its efficient parameter updates. QDoRA has the lowest memory allocation (around $2 \cdot 10^9$ bytes) due to fine-tuning applying quantization, but this results in slower training. Full fine tuning is best for scenarios with abundant resources, while LoRA and DoRA balance memory efficiency and speed, making them suitable for more constrained environments. QDoRA excels in memory and power efficiency but sacrifices speed.

LLM's carbon footprint comes from energy consumption during training, primarily using GPUs, highlighting the need for accurate impact assessments for environmental mitigation [19]. The GPU temperature graph in Figure 6 illustrates the energy efficiency of four models during training by tracking GPU temperatures over time. AraT5v2-Base-with-QDoRA maintains a stable temperature around $44 - 48^\circ C$, indicating steady, efficient GPU usage over 10 hours. AraT5v2 full fine tuning shows the highest temperature spikes, peaking at $65^\circ C$ during its fast 2-hour training, reflecting high power consumption and a larger carbon footprint. QDoRA and LoRA had moderate temperatures, between 40 and 51 degrees, offering efficient GPU usage but slightly more power than LoRA. AraT5v2-Base-with-DoRA operates at the lowest temperature of $36 - 37^\circ C$, making it the most energy-efficient model with the smallest environmental impact. The graph in the Figure 7 below shows GPU utilization for the different techniques applied on araT5v2 Base. The Full fine tuning peaks at 71%, reflecting again its high computational intensity and fast training time of around 2 hours. In contrast, LoRA and DoRA demonstrate moderate GPU utilization, with LoRA having quicker training than DoRA. Lastly, QDoRA operates between 27-34%, with the longest training time, over 10 hours, prioritizing energy efficiency. Each variant balances speed and resource consumption differently, with Full fine tuning being the fastest and QDoRA the most power-efficient and the slowest.

All variations of araT5v2 show fluctuating CPU usage over time according to Figure 8, with peaks reaching 100% utilization at various points, indicating varying computational intensity during different phases of training, with full fine tuning finishes fast and QDoRA takes the longest period as shown before. These techniques primarily affect the duration of CPU usage rather than the intensity of CPU

Figure 6: GPU Temperature in araT5v2

Figure 7: GPU Usage in % in araT5v2

utilization.

5.1.2 NLLB200 600M

The table 6 presents trainable Parameters in the other techniques, in full fine tuning, all the parameters are trained and updated. We examined the trade-offs between GPU power consumption and training speed for the NLLB200-600M model using different fine-tuning techniques. Full fine-tuning consumes the most power, reaching up to 95%, but trains the fastest by updating all model parameters, making it computationally intensive. LoRA uses the lowest power (40-50%) while having the slowest training speed, making it more resource-efficient. DoRA, with power usage around 55-68%, is faster than LoRA

Figure 8: System CPU Usage in % in araT5v2

Table 6: Comparison of trainable Parameters on NLLB200-600M

Optimization	Trainable Parameters	Total Parameters	Percentage of Trainable Parameters
LoRA	1,179,648	616,253,440	0.19%
DoRA	1,253,376	616,253,440	0.20%
QLoRA	1,179,648	616,253,440	0.19%

Figure 9: GPU power consumption in % in NLLB200-600M

due to optimized parameter updates while still being more power-efficient than full fine-tuning. QLoRA, despite leveraging quantization for memory efficiency, has high power consumption (82-97%) and requires substantial GPU power at times. Overall, DoRA offers a better balance of power efficiency and speed,

Figure 10: GPU power consumption in Watt in NLLB200-600M

while full fine-tuning and QLoRA prioritizes speed at the cost of high resource use.

Figure 11: GPU memory allocated in NLLB200-600M

The graph presented in Figure 11 shows the GPU memory allocation over time for various fine-tuning methods of the NLLB200-600M model. Full fine-tuning consumes the most memory, peaking at $1.51 \cdot 10^{10}$ bytes and remaining constant till the end of its training. DoRA and QLoRA exhibit gradual memory increases, stabilizing at $1.09 \cdot 10^{10}$ and $9.38 \cdot 10^9$ bytes, respectively, making them more memory efficient (especially QLoRA). LoRA also shows a gradual increase but experiences fluctuations before stabilizing around $1.06 \cdot 10^{10}$ bytes. Overall, QLoRA is notably the most memory efficient technique, while LoRA shows some instability before leveling off, but takes more time training.

Figure 12 shows the GPU temperature over time for different training methods: The DoRA, QLoRA

Figure 12: GPU temperature in NLLB200-600M

and full finetuning methods maintain a relatively high and stable temperature, hovering around $75-77^{\circ}C$. There are minor fluctuations, but overall, the temperature remains steady. The LoRA method shows more balance in temperature, ranging between $56-61^{\circ}C$, with noticeable dips and rises. It operates at a generally lower temperature compared to the other methods. The Figure 13 shows GPU utilization

Figure 13: GPU utilization in NLLB200-600M

over time for different methods: Full fine tuning has high GPU utilization, often reaching around 78%. There are occasional drops, but it generally maintains a high level of resource usage, indicating intensive processing. QLoRA also shows relatively high utilization, fluctuating between 49% and 60% and DoRA has moderate utilization, around 26%-35%, indicating a balanced approach between performance and resource usage. LoRA shows the lowest GPU utilization, generally staying below 30%, reflecting a more

optimized use of resources. In general, Full finetuning and QLoRA make the most aggressive use of GPU resources.

Figure 14: System CPU utilization in NLLB200-600M

The graph in Figure 14 displays system CPU utilization over time for different methods: DoRA and LoRA exhibit high variability with frequent spikes in CPU usage, often reaching above 80, this indicates intensive CPU involvement and processing. QLoRA in Figure 15 maintains the most balanced CPU utilization, with fewer and lower spikes. NLLB200-600M full finetuning displays low and most stable CPU utilization. In total, DoRA and LoRA show more intensive and variable CPU usage, while QLoRA and full finetuning use CPU resources more efficiently and steadily.

In a comparative analysis of fine-tuning methods across models, distinct trade-offs show up in terms of performance, resource usage, and training efficiency. Full Fine-Tuning updates all model parameters, making it the most computationally intensive approach. It achieves the fastest training speed but consumes the most GPU power and memory, limiting its practicality in memory-constrained environments. LoRA and DoRA, which fine-tune a smaller subset of parameters, and QLoRA, which also introduces quantization to further reduce memory and computation demands, offer a compromise. They significantly reduce GPU memory consumption and power usage, with LoRA showing moderate memory access. DoRA has slightly higher power usage than LoRA but converges faster in some cases, making it ideal for scenarios where power efficiency is crucial but training speed remains important. QDoRA, which introduces quantization to further reduce memory and computation demands, uses the least memory, but the added quantization complexity causes occasional GPU power spikes and slower training speeds compared to LoRA. This makes it suitable for extreme memory-constrained environments, regardless of trade-off in speed and performance.

5.2 Translation Quality comparison

5.2.1 Evaluation metrics results

According to the following Bar chart :

Full Fine-Tuning achieves the highest ROUGEL and SacreBLEU scores compared to the other methods. QDoRA and DoRA show nearly identical performance. LoRA shows a similar ROUGE score as DoRA and QDoRA but seems to slightly underperform them in SacreBLEU and Perplexity. While Full Fine-Tuning provides the best results, the gap between LoRA-based methods and Full Fine-Tuning is not large. This reinforces the idea that LoRA-based methods offer a good balance between performance and computational efficiency, especially when full fine-tuning is resource-prohibitive.

Figure 15: NLLB200-600M-QLoRA system CPU utilization

Figure 16: Bar Chart showing comparative araT5v2 Evaluation Using ROUGEL, SacreBLEU, in addition to Perplexity

Figure 17: Bar Chart showing comparative NLLB200-600M Evaluation Using ROUGEL, SacreBLEU, in addition to Perplexity

According to Figure 17, The full fine-tuning method starts at a higher ROUGEL and SacreBLEU

scores and remains ahead of all parameter-efficient methods. DoRA and LoRA show almost identical performance, with DoRA slightly edging out. QLoRA remains the lowest performer. The perplexity shows that the uniformity of perplexity scores across all methods shown here is notable. It implies that, in terms of understanding and predicting the structure of the target language, all methods are equally effective.

Full fine-tuning offers the best evaluation scores results, but parameter-efficient methods like DoRA and LoRA are closely following, suggesting they provide a competitive trade-off between performance and resource usage.

5.2.2 Human evaluation results

In our inference tests, Arabic sentences were translated using AraT5v2 and compared with Google Translate. For simple sentences, all fine-tuning methods (Table 7) performed similarly, showing that lightweight techniques like LoRA and QDoRA can handle basic translations effectively. However, errors in complex sentences - especially with idiomatic expressions - revealed significant limitations. Google Translate generally outperformed the fine-tuned models in these cases, delivering more fluent translations, while the models often struggled with figurative language, producing more literal or incomplete outputs.

Noticeably, some Arabic words remained untranslated across all fine-tuning methods, indicating gaps in vocabulary handling. Full Fine-Tuning provided the best overall performance but occasionally overcomplicated translations, likely due to overfitting.

For NLLB200-600M (Table 8), all fine-tuning methods closely matched Google Translate on straightforward sentences but diverged on abstract phrases. Overall, Full Fine-Tuning excelled but was resource-heavy, while LoRA and DoRA offered a balanced trade-off, and QLoRA proved best suited for extreme memory constraints but was slower to converge.

Table 9 presents comparison between GPT models BLEU scores and ours, due to hardware limitations, we were unable to use similarly powerful models in our experiments, resulting in comparatively lower performance to the results we presented in the related works.

6 Conclusion

This study explored the trade-offs between computational efficiency and Arabic-to-English translation quality in LLMs, focusing on parameter-efficient fine-tuning techniques, particularly variations of LoRA. While full fine-tuning showed optimal translation accuracy, LoRA and DoRA achieved comparable quality with reduced computational costs remarkably. QLoRA offered additional memory efficiency, though at the expense of longer training time. Future work will explore scaling these methods to larger models and enhancing their capacity to capture complex linguistic structures. All code and models are provided in a [GitHub repository](#) as open source, editable Jupyter notebooks.

Table 7

Translations generated by araT5v2

Arabic original text	DoRA	Full fine tuning	LoRA	QDoRA	Google Translate
قررت أن أغير وظيفتي لأبحث عن فرص جديدة	I have decided to change my job to find new opportunities	I decided to change my job to seek new opportunities	I decided to change my job to find new opportunities.	I decided to change my job to find new opportunities.	I decided to change my job to look for new opportunities
السيف أصدقُ إنباءً مِنَ الكُتُبِ في حدِه الحدُ بينَ الحِدِّ واللَّعِبِ	The spend of books is stronger from the table of books, in the same line between the study and the game	The cost estimate provides for the highest number of newspapers at the extent of	The spend of books is expenditure at the line of the line between the and game.	The printing of books are expenditure to the time and the game.	The sword is more truthful than books in its sharpness, the line between seriousness and play.
السيف اصدق انباء من الكتب في حدِه الحد بين الحِدِّ واللَّعِبِ	السيف is the most accurate of books, in the scale of the time and game.	The sword is the most best source of books at the time of serious and play	The السيف is most accurate of books in the same line between serious and game.	The السيف is the best evidence of books in the same line between the argument and play	The sword is more truthful than books in its sharpness, the limit between seriousness and play

Table 8

Translations generated by NLLB200-600M

Arabic original text	DoRA	Full fine tuning	LoRA	QLoRA	Google Translate
قررت أن أغير وظيفتي لأبحث عن فرص جديدة	I decided to change jobs to look for new opportunities.	I decided to change jobs to look for new opportunities	I decided to change jobs to look for new opportunities.	I decided to change jobs to look for new opportunities.	I decided to change my job to look for new opportunities
السيف أصدقُ إنباءً مِنَ الكُتُبِ في حدِه الحدُ بينَ الحِدِّ واللَّعِبِ	The sword I believe is a book narrative about the boundary between grandfather and play.	The sword. I believe a prophecy from a book alone about the boundary between seriousness and play	I believe the sword is a book narrative about the boundary between grandfather and play.	I believe the sword is a book narrative about the boundary between grandfather and play.	The sword is more truthful than books in its sharpness, the line between seriousness and play
السيف اصدق انباء من الكتب في حدِه الحد بين الحِدِّ واللَّعِبِ	The sword believes prophecies from books about the boundary between grandpa and play.	The sword believed the prophecies of the books in the boundary between grandfather and play.	The sword believes prophecies from books about the boundary between grandfather and play.	Sword believes prophecies from books about the boundary between grandfather and play.	The sword is more truthful than books in its sharpness, the limit between seriousness and play

Table 9

BLEU Scores for GPT Language Models compared to araT5v2 Base and NLLB200-600M

Model	BLEU score
GPT-4	~45
ChatGPT	~40
araT5v2 Full fine tuning	19.951
araT5v2 Full LoRA	12.531
araT5v2 Full DoRA	13.006
araT5v2 Full QDoRA	13.027
NLLB200-600M Full fine tuning	34.245
NLLB200-600M LoRA	32.676
NLLB200-600M DoRA	32.812
NLLB200-600M QLoRA	31.595

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